

The eligibility of the dose spillage in stereotactic radiotherapy evaluated with an in-house-written program

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Abstract. The *dvhanal* in-house written program developed previously, which allows the user to examine the dose coverage of the PTV and the dose limits of the OARs from the DVH file, and to evaluate whether the radiotherapy plan meets the protocol prescriptions. For the evaluation of the dose spillage in SRS planning, the *dvhanal* program was modified, and the *dvhsrs* add-on was written.

Introduction

The *dvhanal* program was written to evaluate the DVH files of RT plans prepared with the Monaco 5.11 treatment planning system (Elekta, Sweden) [1]. The program runs under Windows 11, it was written in QB64, and the GUI was implemented in Python 3.11. The **absolute** DVH file of the RT plan is exported from the TPS. The program also requires a protocol prescription file, which stores the list of tasks for collecting the quantities from the DVH data file, the per-protocol, and acceptable variation values.

Materials and Methods

For evaluation of the dose spillage in stereotactic (SRS) planning, additional data are required as follows:

- the Prescription dose,
- the maximal (D(0,03ccm)) dose in the PTV,
- the maximal dose at 2 cm apart from the PTV,
- the maximal dose out of the PTV.
- Volume of the 50% isodose surface,

Table 1. illustrates the mandatory tasks and the added commands (C,P).

Lung SRS 50=5*10Gy				PP	VA
				cGy	cGY
PTV	D	0,03	ccm <	6000	7500 cGy
PTV	V	5000	cGy >	98	95 %
PTV	P	5000	cGy <	0	0 cGy
PTV	C	0	ccm <	0	0 ccm
PTV	N	0	ccm >	4500	0 cGy
PTV	V	5000	cGy >	0	0 ccm
PTV	V	2500	cGy >	0	0 ccm
Pat-PTV+2	D	0,03	ccm <	0	0 cGy
Pat-PTV	D	0,03	ccm <	0	0 cGy
V_50	C	0	ccm <	0	0 ccm

Table 1. The mandatory tasks (sample) in the protocol prescription file for evaluation of the dose spillage

Command P: sets the Prescription dose,

Command C: writes the value of the PTV volume,

Command N: writes the minimal dose value in the PTV

structure Pat-PTV: External contour - PTV,

structure Pat-PTV+2 is the External contour- PTV extended with 2cm in all directions,

structure V_50 is the isodose surface generated with the 50% of the Prescription dose.

(The latter three structures should be also included in the exported DVH.txt file)

According to the RTOG 0813 and RTOG 0915 protocols, the per-protocol and acceptable variation values depend on the PTV volume. Two additional files: *psrsd2cm.csv* and *psrsrR50.csv* were created with the protocol prescription file format to store the per-protocol and acceptable variation values with different PTV volumes as seen in Table 3. and 4. in the Appendix.

The *dvhsrs* program reads the *Report.csv* file generated by the *dvhanal* program, and also reads the *psrsd2cm.csv* and *psrsr5.csv* files, selects the per-protocol and acceptable variation values on the PTV volume, and generates the *srsreport.csv* file illustrated in Table 2.

However, the per protocol and acceptable variation values are pertinent to the Lung cases: they can be applied for other locations[2]. The GUI was also updated.

Prescription dose				5000 cGy	
max dose				6501 cGy	
maxdos/prescription dose				1,3002	
max dose at 2cm				3279 cGy	
max dose at 2cm/presd	50	57		65,58 %	uv
PTV_volume				31 ccm	
V_50_volume				162 ccm	
V_50/PTV volume	5,9	7,5		5,225806 pp	

Table 2. The SRS plan dose spillage report (uv: unacceptable, va: acceptable variation, pp: per protocol).

Installation

Unzip the dvhanalsrs.zip file, create the [C:\dvhanal](#) folder with r/w attributes, copy the extracted folders work and protocols to the dvhanal map. Run the qui.exe program.

Disclaimer. The program comes without any warranty, and has not been approved for clinical use by any regulatory bodies. Use at your own risk.

Appendix

srs_max dose at 2cm				PP	VA
PTV	2	1 ccm	<	50	57 %
PTV	2	18 ccm	<	50	57 %
PTV	2	38 ccm	<	50	57 %
PTV	2	74 ccm	<	50	58 %
PTV	2	132 ccm	<	50	58 %
PTV	2	220 ccm	<	54	63 %
PTV	2	340 ccm	<	58	68 %
PTV	2	500 ccm	<	62	77 %
PTV	2	700 ccm	<	66	86 %
PTV	2	950 ccm	<	70	89 %
PTV	2	1260 ccm	<	73	91 %

Table 3. The srsrd2cm.csv file

				PP*10	VA *10
PTV	R	1 ccm	<	59	75
PTV	R	18 ccm	<	59	75
PTV	R	38 ccm	<	55	65
PTV	R	74 ccm	<	51	60
PTV	R	132 ccm	<	47	58
PTV	R	220 ccm	<	45	55
PTV	R	340 ccm	<	43	53
PTV	R	500 ccm	<	40	50
PTV	R	700 ccm	<	35	48
PTV	R	950 ccm	<	33	44
PTV	R	1260 ccm	<	31	40
PTV	R	1630 ccm	<	29	37

Table 4. The psrsr50.csv file

References

1. Palvolgyi, J. (2025). A simple in-house-written program for examination of eligibility of the radiotherapy plans for the protocol prescriptions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16285650>
2. Linda H. SBRT Treatment Planning: Practical Considerations
<https://amos3.aapm.org/abstracts/pdf/68-19774-234349-85603.pdf>